

Social Media and National Security in Nigerian State

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Abstract

This study examined the nexus between social media and national security in Nigeria. This study sourced information from the secondary data. Social media are referred to as interactive (web 2.0) internet-based applications where users can generate content(s) and share which is a welcome development as against the traditional media. But unfortunately, when social media sites are not properly checkmated by forensic computer analysts/regulatory agencies, it can be catastrophic or threat to the national security of a country. From the study, the following findings were observed: It was discovered that the Nigerian Communications Act (2003) is not very effective as regards regulating the social media most especially in the area of content sharing. It was also discovered that in Nigeria, there is poor enforcement of the Freedom of Information Act and Nigerian Communications Commission low technological base via the provision of a gateway to control the information space as it obtains in China and other developed countries of the world. As a result of the above findings, the following recommendations were made: The Nigeria Government should ensure that her Nigerian Communications Act (NCA) 2003 is strengthened enough to contain security challenges in Nigeria. The federal government should ensure that freedom of information act is fully implemented by the government institutions to avoid creating room for generation of fake news/fake content and that the technological bases of regulatory agencies like NCC are sufficiently provided for to be able to work effectively.

Keywords: Social Media, National, Security, State, Nigeria

1. Introduction

The idea of *social media* has a long history of account dating back to the 1970s. According to Wikipedia, ARPANET, which first came online in 1967, had by the late 1970s developed a rich cultural exchange of non-government/business ideas and communication, as clearly evidenced by ARPANET. Social media as we have it today are interactive system/computer-mediated technologies that support the creation and sharing of data, ideas, career interests and other forms of expression via virtual communities and networks (Wikipedia, n.d).

However, there are some popular features of social media: Social media are referred to as interactive Web 2.0 Internet-based applications, user generated content(s), like text posts, digital photos, videos, and data generated through all online interactions. Which however, serve as "lifeblood" or strength of social media, through which users can create service specific profiles for the website or app that are designed and maintained by the social media organization, and again, Social media supports and facilitate the development of online social networks by connecting a user's profile with those of other individuals or groups. According to Wikipedia, users typically access social media services via web-based technologies on desktops and laptops, or download services that offer social media functionality to their mobile devices such as smartphones and tablets. When engaging with these services, users take advantage of creating highly interactive platforms through which individuals, communities, and organizations can share, co-create, discuss, and modify user-generated content(s) or pre-made content(s) posted online. They "introduce substantial and pervasive changes to communication between organizations, communities, and individuals". However, social media changes the way individuals and large organizations communicate and these changes are the focus of the emerging fields of *technoself* studies. Social media is different from paper-based media (e.g., magazines and newspapers) to traditional electronic media such as TV broadcasting in many ways, including quality, reach, frequency, interactivity, usability, immediacy, and performance. Again, social media outlets operate in a dialogic transmission system (many sources to many receivers), which is in contrast to traditional media which operates under a monologic transmission model (one source to many receivers), for example, a newspaper which is delivered to many subscribers, or a radio station which broadcasts the same programs to an entire city. Some of the famous social

media websites are Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Snapchat, Twitter, and Whatsapp. According to Wikipedia, these social media websites have more than 100,000,000 registered users (Wikipedia, n.d).

According to a report by Global Digital Statistic cited in Deen (n.d), shows that there are about 2 billion social network active users in the world. This represents 28% of the total world population, i.e., at least, in every four; one is using the social network. Furthermore, according to the report revealed by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) indicates that Nigeria has the largest users of the internet in Africa, with over 43.9 million internet users, representing 25% of the country's population. In the month of March 2013, World Bank ranked Nigeria as the third highest users of Facebook in Africa, with total active users of 5,534,160 (PM News, 2013 in Deen, n.d). In 2012, according to Portland Communications, a kenyan based public relation agency, as well placed Nigeria as the third tweeting country in Africa (Punch Newspaper, 2012 in Deen, n.d).

Furthermore, in the account of Nigerian blog awards, there are about 1 million blogs own and update by Nigerians and the numbers are continuously growing in popularity and the above figures show the rapid penetration of the new media in the African continent and Nigeria particular (Deen, n.d)

On the other hand, *National Security* can be referred to like the security of a nation state, including its citizens, economy, and institutions, and hence regarded as a duty of government. Originally conceived as a protection against military attack, national security is further widely understood to include non-military dimensions, including economic security, energy security, environmental security, food security, cyber security, etc. Similarly, national security risks include, in addition to the actions of other nation states, action by violent non-state actors, narcotic cartels, and multinational corporations, and also the effects of natural disasters. Governments rely on a range of measures, including political, economic, and military power, as well as diplomacy to enforce national security (Wikipedia, n.d).

National security according to Macmillan Dictionary (n.d) is the protection or the safety of a country's secrets and its citizens. It is also a prerequisite for progress and orderliness in any society and this is because the protection of lives and property is paramount in the life of man (Ogunmola-Daomi, 2015).

However, having examined the variables; thus, this study was embarked upon to verify the impact of social media on national security.

2. Impact of Social Media on National Security

In the Nigerian state, over 87.37 percent of social media activities are conducted on Facebook. The National Communications Commission (NCC) attributes 74 percent of this traffic to 32,513,261 young Nigerians who use mobile devices (Beckley, 2018).

This new media eliminates the gatekeeping mechanism of traditional media, which has allowed a large number of youth the freedom to communicate anonymously thereby resulting from directing hate filled comments to other Nigerians. Such actions generate and fuel hatred, which then leads to acts of individual and collective violence which pose significant threats to national security. Accordingly, the Nigerian government adopted measures, including establishing the Nigeria Internet Registration Association and other organizations which censor content deemed offensive to the Nigerian community (Beckley, 2018).

Also, the National Assembly passed the Prohibition of Frivolous Petitions and Other Related Matters Act 2017, which popularly, termed the 'social media bill' that aims to censor aspects of conduct on social media. These steps have failed to curtail hate speech, incitement to violence and other criminal activities conducted over social media in Nigeria. The lack of synergy among relevant agencies in charge of digital communication inhibits greater achievement of the unified efforts of the individual agencies that are assigned either advocacy or control responsibility on social media. This resulted in the absence of a designated body endowed with the responsibility to clamp down on perpetrators of abuses on the social media, civil violations and social media related crimes. There is no agency currently saddled with the responsibility and requisite enablement to filter social media postings that constitute a threat to national security and track the perpetrators as well as site owners in order to bring them to justice. The absence of a regulating body or law for social media users means that messages can be sent without being monitored nor censured regardless of its possible effects on national security (Beckley, 2018).

On the other hand, social media has created a cost effective means of participatory political discourse. It gives voices to voiceless people and community. It enables members of the larger society to broadcast their feelings without necessarily seeking the services of journalists. It empowers users to get first-hand information and also allows them to contribute and rebroadcast what they read with other users (Deen, n.d).

3. Management of Social Media

According to Beckley (2018), one major challenge as regards to management of social media in Nigeria is the lack of regulatory law in the Nigerian Communications Act (NCA) 2003. In China, the use of social media is regulated, as over 642 internet users are censored per minute to enhance the national security of China due to the regulatory mechanism in place. In Nigeria, Subsection 11 (i) of the NCA 2003 only seeks to hype, support and safeguard national interests, safety and security in the use of the said scarce national resources without mentioning how social media could be regulated. Again, section 37 of the constitution of Nigeria guarantees the right to "the privacy of citizens" which essentially implies privacy in the broad sense and not just privacy of homes, correspondence, telephone conversations and telegraphic communications that follow. Hence, from the constitutional right to privacy, certain information gathered from Nigerians to form various databases, particularly in the telecommunications industry is protected. The poor enforcement of the Freedom of Information Act and NCC due to the low technological base via the provision of a gateway to control the information space as it obtains in China has led to the indiscriminate use of social media in information security, which has led to infringement of privacy. There are over 20 social media sites where information could be passed to the public without any form of restriction, which includes Facebook, YouTube, Twitter and among others.

The growth of social networks during the last decade has been astonishing with over 200 active social networking sites. Information on these sites can only be monitored, analysed and investigated through forensic computer analysts and social network forensic experts amongst others. There is a dearth of manpower in these areas to address some of the negative challenges of social network on national security. However, forensic computer analysts can go a long way in filling the lacuna existing therein. Hence they make of forensic tools and software to extract and analyse data, deal with highly sensitive data and collect information as well as evidence in a legally admissible way, amongst others. Increased manpower in these fields will help address the negative effects of social network on national security (Beckley, 2018).

4. Findings

1. It was discovered that the Nigerian Communications Act (2003) is not very effective as regards regulating the social media specifically, in the area of content sharing.
2. It was discovered that in Nigeria, there is poor enforcement of the Freedom of Information Act and NCC due to the low technological base via the provision of a gateway to control the information space as it obtains in China and other developed countries of the world.
3. It was also discovered that in Nigeria, there is a poor number of forensic computer analysts.

5. Recommendations to the findings

As a result of the above findings, the following recommendations should be adequately followed as regards to the subject matter:

1. The Nigeria government should ensure that her Nigerian Communications Commission (2003) is strengthened enough to contain security challenges in Nigeria.
2. The federal government should ensure that freedom of information act is fully implemented by the government institutions to avoid creating room for generation of fake news/fake content and that the technological bases of regulatory agencies like NCC are sufficiently provided for to be able to work effectively.
3. The federal government should increase the workforce of forensic computer analysts so as to perform effectively and efficiently in social media sites.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of social media on national security in Nigeria. In the study, we realized that coming of social network/social media is a welcome development in the world because of the fact that, it educates, entertains and helps in connecting friends and so forth. But it has a bad side to it. It can easily be used to pass fake information which most times could cause pandemonium in a community. As a result of that, we are of the opinion that the Nigerian government should ensure that the needful and every necessary need of regulatory agencies are well provided to avoid bad elements in the society taking advantage of the social media.

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